

CALiMERO

IMPROVING BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES LIFE CYCLE SUSTAINABILITY

D6.3. Communication and dissemination plan

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PROJECT INFORMATION

Project full title: Industry CAse Studies AnaLysis To IMprove EnviROnmental Performance And Sustainability Of Bio-Based Industrial Processes

Acronym: CALIMERO

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-06 - Increasing the environmental performance of industrial processes in bio-based sectors: construction, woodworking, textiles, pulp and paper and bio-chemicals

Start date: 1st July 2022

Duration: 48 months

List of participants:

Partner No.	PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION ACRONYM
1 (Coord.)	Contactica CTA
2	WeLOOP WELOOP
3	European Cellulose Insulation Association ECIA
4	Swedish Environmental Research Institute IVL
5	Neovili NEOVILI
6	Cesefor CESEFOR
7	Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology LIST
8	Technical University of Denmark DTU
9	Techtera TECHTERA
10	Essity ESSITY
11	BIM Kemi AB BIMKEMI
12	Ereks garment EREKS

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Document Number:	D6.3
Document Title:	Communication and Dissemination Plan
Dissemination level	PU – Public, fully open,
Period:	PR1
WP:	WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Task:	T6.2
Author:	Contactica SL
Abstract:	<p>The communication and dissemination plan clarifies the messages, strategies and channels that will be used throughout the CALIMERO project.</p> <p>This is a living document which may suffer slight modifications throughout the duration of the project, if necessary, to keep counting on a tailor-made strategy to achieve all the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set at the beginning of the project. The plan details how CALIMERO's communication and dissemination will be carried out by all members of the consortium with specific actions.</p>

Version	Date	Description
Version 1	30/12/2022	Initial version

1 INTRODUCTION

CALIMERO is an acronym to name the project called originally “*Industry CAse studies anaLysis to IMprove EnviROnmental performance and sustainability of bio-based industrial processes*”. The main goal of the project is to standardize Life Cycle Assessment methodologies among certain sectors of bio-based industries for them to become more sustainable from different perspectives.

In the **current context of the European Union in which 51% of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions are produced by the continent’s industries**, it is urgent to find ways to reduce them and deal with all pollutant releases without causing any other significant harm to other sustainability areas. **Transitioning to a bioeconomy or a bio-based low-carbon economy with circular material flows** is a high political priority at all levels, being part of the European Union Industrial Policy Strategy, the European Green Deal, the 2030 Climate Target Plan and the Bioeconomy strategy.

It is also necessary to assess the environmental burdens shifting produced by this transition using reliable methodologies. The **PEF (Product Environmental Footprint)**, developed by the European Union to ensure harmonization among Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodologies for products, **presents relevant gaps for sustainability measurements for bio-based industrial processes: biodiversity and ecosystem services impacts assessment methodologies, relevant toxicity characterization factors as well as dynamic systems to account GHG emissions or methods to include circularity, criticality and socio-economic indicators.**

Current methods lack of some important factors which will be taken into account in order to have a broader picture of bio-based industries’ sustainability performance. Improving current methodologies, then, is **key towards finding greener and more sustainable solutions.**

In consequence, the project aims to establish a frame for bio-based industries to evolve in all PEF indicators, plus those added by **CALIMERO**. The participation of the mentioned bio-based industries in the consortium will help identifying and proposing sectorial and cross-sectorial solutions to **tackle sustainability hotspots**. With these data and analysis in hand, specific guidelines and recommendations will be developed. The objective is to **contribute to a more sustainable economy and to spread these guidelines for other bio-based industries to follow the lead.**

In term of communication, **CALIMERO** is a **quite technical project, but whose complexities should not be very difficult to adapt and explain to different potential audiences and stakeholders**. The combination of different channels, messages and tools is key to impact different publics with various purposes.

The presence of several sectors from the bio-based industries makes it easier for the communication to be more effective as well as to **perform a more active networking activity**. This is the best way to **prepare the ground for the final guidelines to spread further** and for many other biobased sectors and industries to follow the same path.

In **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, it is possible to visualize the communication strategy that **CALIMERO** team will follow during the project. As showed in the figure, the strategy lays in different channels and actions that require a common effort between the Work Package leader (Contactica) and the rest of the consortium members. The tools and details in this figure will be **combined and used properly throughout the project** aiming to achieve the maximum visibility for each specific target group. Along this communication and dissemination plan, strategies, messages and channels will be explained to plan how to address specific audiences and reach the project goals.

Figure 1. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

All projects have the need of a strong communication, but **those aiming to reach the general public need to double efforts** for their message to impact the maximum number of people. Addressing general public is a challenge that **CALIMERO** can overcome through **strong messages and different channels and approaches**. For the most specialized audience, dissemination tools and

approaches can be used.

Three kinds of **general audiences**

will be addressed during the project and several **tailored approaches** will be used for communication purposes, as showed in Figure 2: general information, informative content (content made within the **CALIMERO** project or developed by other sources) visual communication materials, dissemination materials, project progress and networking. All audiences, channels and approaches will be detailed later on in this document.

Figure 2. Tailored approaches

2 OBJECTIVES

These are the main objectives of the communication and dissemination plan.

- Promote the visibility of **CALIMERO** activities, goals and outcomes during project implementation.
- Raise awareness of the importance of the consumption of bio-based products rather than petroleum-based.
- Engage all target audiences with didactic contents and activities.

Achieving them depends on several factors but strong and tailor-made communication, dissemination and exploitation during the project can be a useful tool, as well as branding.

3 BRANDING

Every company, institution and project need a **recognizable brand** in order for people to find them. And, also,

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in order to achieve all the communication objectives and **maximize the project visibility**. To get a good branding, there are various elements to take into account.

3.1 Name

As stated before, the project's name is an **acronym** formed putting together the letters of this title: *Industry CAse studies anaLysis to IMprove EnviRONmental performance and sustainability of bio-based industrial processes*.

This title must always be written **under quotation marks**, when used for communication purposes, and, after, the acronym can be written with **capital letters**, preferably in green color with this color code: **#93C255**

3.2 Logo

With every brand name comes a logo, to make it easier for people to **identify the project**. The **CALIMERO** logo contains the project's name and visual elements to ease the comprehension of its topic.

The project's logo is divided into 3 different parts:

- a) **Logotype:** the word contained in the image. The use of the typography is really important to reflect the project's personality. The use of a specific typography strengthens it and makes sure there is clarity and harmony in all communications.

The selected typography for **CALIMERO's** logo is a modified variant of Bodoni.

With it on the logo, **universality with a distinctive touch** is shown.

Bodoni is a Roman typographic family with a modern touch. His creator was Giambattista Bodoni. The deep contrasts in its proportions, the uniform width of its characters as well as the straight and thin angles give this typography a **clear and expressive appearance**.

- b) **Symbol:** the symbol of the logo is located on top of the logotype. It is the shape of a C with a green dot in the center, which is connected to another green dot on its right side. This dot is connected to other 5 dots that surround the C creating an open pentagon around.

- c) **Slogan:** the slogan below **CALIMERO**'s name is "*Improving bio-based industries life cycle sustainability*". This slogan summarizes the main activity and goal of the project. It is written with the typography *Raleway Light*.

3.2.1 Logo variations and uses

- The positive logo **in green** is the recommended version for the majority of communication uses.
- The positive logo with chromatic variations and use of the **secondary colour**, turquoise green, can be used in other materials.

3.3 **Visual identity**

The visual identity of the project, like the logo and the name, is the way **CALIMERO** is presented in a visual way. This is the way to **create a first impression** on anyone outside the project and, once in contact with it, of them to **remember it** through different tools. To conform the visual identity, two elements are necessary: **colours** and **typography**.

3.3.1 Colours

These colours have been picked to **align with the project logo**. All of them must be used in documents, PowerPoint presentations, communication materials and **any communication piece regarding the project**.

The name and code facilitate the printing process of any **CALIMERO** communication material.

Colour name	CMYK	Pantone	RGB	HEX	Graphic colour
Green	C044 M000 Y075 K000	419C	R164 G213 B093	#93c255	
Black	C074 M064 Y062 K081	419C	R030 G030 B028	#1e1e1c	
Turquoise green	C061 M004 Y031 K000	7541C	R97 G191 B188	#61bfbc	
Blue-green	C060 M000 Y002 K060	-	R041 G102 B100	#296664	
Grey	C000 M000 Y000 K009	-	R231 G230 B230	#E7E6E6	
Olivine	C016 M000 Y028 K024	-	R163 G195 B141	#a3c38d	
Dark Green	C100 M000 Y100 K061	-	R000 G100 B000	#006400	
Ecru-white	C001 M000 Y004 K003	-	R245 G248 B239	#f5f8ef	

3.3.2 Typography

As stated before, typography is an important part of branding. So, from now on, this is the **typography**, which will be used in all communication and dissemination materials of the **CALIMERO** project. Either of these typographies can be used indistinctly.

BODONI

Bold

A B C D E F G H I J K L M
N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
a b c d e f g h i j k l m
n o p q r s t u v w x y z

Bodoni Sans Text

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Ññ Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1234567890 / * - + = ¿ ? ¡ ! ” # % & () ; : . , - _ “ ” [] { } Çç < > ‘ ’ ° ª \ @ ~ ~ ^

Arial Nova Condensed

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Ññ Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1234567890 / * - + = ¿ ? ¡ ! ” # % & () ; : . , - _ “ ” [] { } Çç < > ‘ ’ ° ª \ @ ~ ~ ^

For the **deliverables**, the preference is using **Arial Nova Condensed**.

4 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

Just like it is important to have a **strong and coherent** visual identity for a project, it is necessary to have the same feeling for the project communication in any way. The first thing for a communication plan is to elaborate a **strategy, which will work as a road map throughout the project**, in order for it to be coherent and to present its core values.

4.1 Target audiences

The first thing to take into account is the **audience** that **CALIMERO** project will be addressing its materials and messages to. **Different audiences need different messages presented in different channels**, so it is key to identify them in the first place. These are the criteria applied to select the different target audiences:

- Interest in the project topics, knowledge shared and development of the different working lines.
- Ability to share any information piece **CALIMERO** produces.
- Involvement in the project.
- Influence over the project and/or the rest of target audiences.
- Ability to maximize any communication and dissemination action.
- Capacity to create synergies and networking.
- Interest in the potential advances of **CALIMERO** to the bio-based industries.
- Potential beneficiaries of **CALIMERO**'s advances.
- Other interested audiences.

With these criteria available, it is easier to determine the **exact groups that the project wants to reach** throughout its duration. **CALIMERO** audiences are these:

- General public.
- Children and high school students.
- Potential girls/women towards the STEM careers.
- Young researchers.
- Bioeconomy associations.

- Bio-based industries and end users.
- Pulp and paper; woodworking; biochemical; construction; and textile bio-based industries.
- Sister EU funded projects.
- Academia.
- Scientific community.
- Life Cycle Assessment associations.
- Sustainability associations and platforms.
- Mass media.
- Institutions and policy makers.

Depending on the public that **CALIMERO** wants to address or the information and content the project produces, there will be **two approaches**:

1. **Communication**: it involves everything related to the project, news about all sectors participating in **CALIMERO** and any piece of information that doesn't contain specific non-public data. Disclosure of some data or information about the project and its work packages is desirable in order to show transparency and expand knowledge, but for scientific and technical data, the dissemination tools are available. The main objective of the project communication is for any piece of information to spread as much as possible and to make the project known for as many people as possible.

Also, **CALIMERO** wants to become **a reliable source of curated and informative content about LCA and the sectors from the project** (woodworking, construction, textile, pulp & paper and biochemical). This means that, in order to be perceived as such, news and content created by others about these topics will be spread through all project channels. And, also, informative content produced in different ways (visual materials, information pieces, etc) will be posted periodically in order to increase the **CALIMERO** community and reinforce this image of a reliable source of sustainability information.

Encouraging children and teenagers to participate and be more actively involved in STEM, as well as pursuing this kind of careers will be addressed through different communication as well as dissemination actions specifically designed of this purpose. This is a specific objective of the communication and dissemination of the project. Specifically, stressing the need of encouraging the vocation towards these careers on girls and young women.

2. **Dissemination**: the dissemination of the project involves the **public disclosure of project-generated results**. It is normally addressed to: researchers, academia, researchers, professionals of different sectors, stakeholders, etc. But dissemination actions with other specific audiences can be performed too, like science weeks for students and general public, who may be interested in **CALIMERO**'s results and progress. Open access in scientific publications will be actively pursued, so any audience can download these results from any specific audience.

4.2 Messages

Once the audience has been identified, it is key to search for **tailor-made messages**. With so many different audiences to reach, it is important to **distribute the project's core values** among different messages and communicate them **through different channels** with specific communicative goals. These messages reflect:

- Main values of the project: **a greener and cleaner Europe; advances on LCA standardization; contributions to bioeconomy; contributions to policy making on bio-based industries; contributions**

to more sustainable bio-based industries from different parameters; utility of LCA as an improvement tool for bio-based industries.

- The project's **evolution**.
- The **goals** that the project aims to achieve.
- **CALIMERO**'s contributions to the **SDGs** of the United Nations, specifically 3 Good health and well-being; 5 Gender equality; 6 Clean water and sanitation; 8 Decent work and economic growth; 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, 10 Reduced Inequalities; 13 Climate Action; 14 Life below water; 15 Life on land.
- The project's **gender balance among the consortium**.
- The importance of **women in STEM**.

It is key to **follow these topics when communicating about the project in all dedicated channels**. These are the selected basic messages for the **CALIMERO** communication strategy:

Table 1. Key messages of the communication strategy

Message	Target groups
Sustainability	General public; children and high-school students; mass media; scientific community; bio-based industries; policy makers
Bioeconomy and bioeconomy contributions	General public; scientific community; mass media; policy makers
Bio-based industries	General public; mass media; scientific community; policy makers
LCA	General public; bio-based industries; mass media; scientific community; policy makers
Biodiversity and ecosystem services related to LCA	General public; bio-based industries; mass media; scientific community; policy makers

4.3 Channels

To address the targeted audiences with the proper messages, **dedicated channels** are needed, as well as **specific actions** throughout the duration of the project. In this chart some of the main communication and dissemination channels and actions are displayed:

Table 2. Channels of the communication strategy

CHANNEL	WHAT
Website https://calimeroproject.eu/	Information and news about the project, its progress and results; project articles and own project events (or with CALIMERO presence).
Twitter @CALIMERO_HE	Information and news about the project, its progress and results; articles related to the CALIMERO subject; links, projects and websites of interest to the stakeholders.
LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/company/calimero-he-project/	Information regarding the project and its development and results: consortium meetings; results; presence at external events, informative content.
Communication materials	Newsletters, brochures, factsheets, infographics. Designed during all the project to raise awareness on important facts, data and/or project progress.

CHANNEL	WHAT
Communication Campaigns	Sending press releases about the project and promoting the project in mass media is vital to achieve the maximum visibility. Also, online campaigns in social media are key to reinforce CALIMERO 's online presence.
Scientific publications	Published in open access to spread technical knowledge about the most specialized audiences.
Workshops and trainings	Organised or co-organised by project partners and inviting experts on specific fields.
Events	Conferences, round table discussions, EU events, networking... These tools may raise awareness of the project and also enrich it.
Partners' existing channels	Partners' websites, social media accounts or platforms can help promote the project activity.
Associations and networks	Like the EuBioNet and networks with other EU funded projects or EU initiatives.

4.3.1 Project's website

CALIMERO project website (<https://calimeroproject.eu/>) was designed as a **visual and user-friendly channel** in order for it to **host the project brand and to provide non-confidential project information**. The navigation through the site is easy and the language used for many of the articles should remain comprehensible and casual to attract as many people from general public as possible. Pieces of information such as project context, core objectives, project structure, impacts and expected outcomes, partners, links to news and events, informative content will be shared periodically in the website. The website will remain operative for at least 3 years after the project completion. **A private area for partners** has been designed in order to ensure an efficient internal communication and store information and deliverables.

4.3.2 Social Media

Social media are a key part of the communication plan. On the one hand, they are **the brand and image of the project** towards people who don't participate in the project. And, on the other hand, they are **the main communication window to reach general public as well as other stakeholders and targeted audiences**. They are also useful to:

- Redirect traffic to the **CALIMERO** website and to raise visitors and page views.
- Create a coherent brand for the project.
- Spread all contents, events, project activities.
- Serve as the visual channel for the project.

CALIMERO will use **Twitter** and **LinkedIn**, unless a different agreement is set or other social networks are proposed. If other channels end up being useful for the projects' objectives, they will be created. There is **gender inequality** present in these social networks, in terms of users, as they are slightly predominantly male-user social networks (The Global State of Digital 2022, Hootsuite). Based on the project statistics in terms of community and followers throughout the project, other channels will be considered, in order to mitigate this.

Also, there is an **age bias**, as a high percentage of many social media users are aged 24-34 years old average, with changes from one channel to another (The Global State of Digital 2022, Hootsuite). The communication of the project will take these facts into account and **will pursue other ways to be able to communicate with all possible audiences**, regardless their age or gender, such as the mentioned science weeks or meetings and workshops designed for younger audiences.

Networking and joint actions will be performed **with other sister EU funded projects** through social media in

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order to grow all projects' visibility and generate more impact. Also, **the help of the partners' channels** is key to maximize the visibility of **CALIMERO** in each and every step of the project.

4.3.3 Communication materials

Communication materials will be designed during the project lifetime to be used by partners when necessary and sometimes to be used as engagement tools for targeted audiences. **CTA**, as leader of WP6 **is responsible for the creation of all communication material, but all partners are allowed to produce their own**, always respecting the branding, visual identity and core project values, and always informing CTA. The main communication materials are:

- **Brochure:** for general communication of the project targets and showing the main objectives, expected outcomes, partners and regions involved.
- **Posters:** to increase visibility of both the project and its partners.
- **Audio-visual and graphic materials:** to help the comprehension of the project.
- **PowerPoint presentation:** updated regularly. It should be used in conferences and external events where partners are participating and should help them explain the project and how it is developing.
- **Roll-up:** for general communication of the project targets and showing the main objectives, expected outcomes, partners and regions involved.
- **Videos:** explanatory videos will be made, showing the achievements of the project and lessons learnt. The target audience will be end-users and policymakers. The video will be promoted via social media and events (e.g., workshops).

When possible, the communication materials and documents will be adapted in terms of accessibility to be read by voice assistants. This will be pursued by titles and sections in documents, in order to be user friendly for these kind of voice assistants, as well as in social media.

4.3.4 Online communication campaigns

With the main aim of **attracting and establishing a CALIMERO community** around our stakeholders and the general public, an online communication strategy has been established with three main pillars:

- The **CALIMERO website will be permanently updated** through the section of news and events.
- **Social Media and newsletters will be used to share the advances** about the project included in the website, and attract visitors and users. Specific calls to action will be published in order to measure engagement and to achieve all communication objectives.
- **Search Engine Optimization (SEO) techniques will be used** to obtain a good positioning of the website on Internet browsers.

4.3.5 Scientific publications

It is expected that the project develops several results from some of the work packages and they will be **addressed to different key scientific communities**. The publications will be made freely and openly available via an online repository. Prior to publishing any scientific publication, the **CALIMERO** partner involved will contact the whole consortium for revision and validation of the publication 45 days in advance. More information for this is presented in Section 7. Dissemination: Open Access.

4.3.6 Workshops

These **sessions will be organized with local stakeholders and different targeted audiences** depending on the specific topic. As the project evolves, different workshops and actions will be organized with various groups of interesting audiences.

Three different lines have been identified in order to organise workshops:

- **Workshops with students:** LCA technology developers, WeLoop, IVL, LIST, CTA, will go to schools and present the projects objectives and advances to students.
- **Workshops with early-career researchers:** CALIMERO's advances can be shown to university students, pre-docs and post-docs (DTU)
- **Workshops with bio-based associations and bio-based industries:** the industrial partners can spread CALIMERO's advances and guidelines with similar stakeholders.

4.3.7 Events

The events are **one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy** because they allow the project members and the project to connect with stakeholders and the general public, encourage networking and show the most important advances and results of the project. **Events also feed of content the communication channels** and tools (website, social media, press releases) generating great impacts on different audiences. They can be in-person events, hybrid, webinars or any kind of dissemination activity that the consortium considers.

The participation of partners in events will be made visible through the CALIMERO website and social media channels contributing to increasing the community of stakeholders and public interested in the project.

General and technical presentations of CALIMERO will be showcased in face-to-face interactions with stakeholders when possible. **CTA will actively look for events, conferences and opportunities** for all members to attend in order to network, enrich the project and spread knowledge about it but, if any member finds interesting events to attend to, it would be useful to communicate it beforehand, so CTA can promote it in all dedicated channels.

Specific actions and joint activities will be organized with sister projects like [ALIGNED](#) project and other similar EU funded projects. This can enable synergies as well as spread the project messages further and generate more visibility for CALIMERO's channels.

4.4 Summary

Communication activities will be carried out actively during the whole project aiming to reach different audiences with various interests and with several objectives. That is why all stakeholders and actors are reflected in the next chart for a better comprehension of the communication and dissemination strategy:

Table 3. Communication Plan

Message	Objectives	Target groups	Channels
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☉ Spread how LCA can make bio-based industries more sustainable. ☉ Communicate the importance of the industries to become more sustainable. ☉ Emphasize how CALIMERO can contribute. 	General public; children and high-school students; mass media; scientific community; bio-based industries; policy makers	Website, social media, scientific publications, communication materials, workshops, events.

Message	Objectives	Target groups	Channels
Bioeconomy and contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☉ Explain what bioeconomy is. ☉ Communicate how CALIMERO can contribute to Europe's bioeconomy by standardizing LCA methodologies. 	General public; scientific community; mass media; policy makers	Website, social media, scientific publications, communication materials, workshops and events.
Bio-based industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☉ Explain what bio-based industries are and how CALIMERO can contribute to them. ☉ Communicate the benefits of bio-based for a greener and more sustainable European industry tissue. 	General public; mass media; scientific community; policy makers	Website, social media, scientific publications, communication materials, workshops, events.
LCA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☉ Explain what LCA is. ☉ Emphasize how the research carried out in the project can make contributions to LCA methodologies. ☉ Communicate how LCA can contribute to bio-based industries' sustainability performance. 	General public; bio-based industries; mass media; scientific community; policy makers	Website, social media, communication materials, workshops, events.
Biodiversity and ecosystem services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☉ Spread how LCA can make bio-based industries more aware of biodiversity and ecosystem services. ☉ Emphasize how CALIMERO can contribute. 	General public; children and high-school students; mass media; scientific community; bio-based industries; policy makers	Website, social media, scientific publications, communication materials, workshops, events.
Specific bio-based sectors of CALIMERO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☉ Explain how woodworking, textiles, biochemical, textile and pulp & paper sectors are contributing to the LCA methodologies improvement. ☉ Communicate how CALIMERO's results can contribute to a more sustainable Europe. ☉ Spread these results and guidelines as further as possible for these and other industries to follow. 	General public; children and high-school students; mass media; scientific community; bio-based industries; policy makers	Website, social media, scientific publications, communication materials, workshops and events.

5 MANAGEMENT OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

CTA is the leader of the WP6 and **coordinates the actions and processes with the inputs of the rest of the members of the consortium**. Additionally, some specific procedures will be designed to organize, in an effective way, the external communication, the generation of content in the website, the social media work, the review of communication and dissemination materials, and the information and reporting about the participation in

events.

It is also CTA's duty to **collect all project communication impacts**, **readjust** the communication plan when needed **and report** to the rest of the consortium. This task, though, is also a collaborative one and all project members are requested to share information of interest to CTA.

5.1 Website

CTA is responsible for the management of the website and will **update regularly** (at least once a month) the **CALIMERO** website with news and events. CTA **will request information from the partners** to prepare the news.

The **events** to which **CALIMERO**'s partners are attending to **have to be promoted** through the website and also from social media. To do it so, partners need to inform CTA beforehand so news can be published. **Members of the consortium are requested to promote** press releases, offer information to create posts on the website, and other content and materials through their own communication tools and channels: website, social media profiles, newsletters, etc.

And they are requested, too, to **provide CTA with photos to upload in every information piece** of the website. For the follow-up of the website, **analytic tools will be used**. These tools will give information regarding the number of visitors, countries, type of business and so on. Reports will be prepared and analysed yearly with the consortium.

5.2 Social media channels

CTA will mainly manage the social media accounts, but all partners can prepare and send information to CTA in order to share interesting information and posts. All contents will be published in English. However, retweets can come from tweets in other languages.

All partners should **follow CALIMERO** social media accounts with their personal/institutional accounts and they should **share** the project social media accounts with their contacts to **create an online network** through different platforms. **CALIMERO** website links to the social media accounts as well as the social media accounts link to the website.

5.2.1 Twitter

Twitter is the most popular micro-blogging site and represents the opportunity to reach people from all over the world with interests related to the project. It is also a requirement from the EU, as all funded projects have a Twitter account.

In addition, it is a good opportunity to create a knowledge network, as all EU institutions and other groups of interest and stakeholders also own Twitter accounts. **CTA is responsible for the management of the Twitter account** for the **CALIMERO** project. **Partners must collaborate** by mentioning the **CALIMERO** accounts, retweeting the messages about the project and sharing publications.

On Twitter, **third parties' content can be shared** if it might result interesting to followers, as it can attract these third parties to follow **CALIMERO** account, raise engagement **and give image of a strong and reliable curated content source**, as stated before. It can be done through retweets or by giving credit to the owner (expressed by the formula "via @name of the original publisher"). Use of #hashtags and @mentions is highly recommended to increase the impact of the tweet. The language will be clear but technical or scientific terms can be used if needed.

These hashtags have been created or considered relevant for **CALIMERO** in Twitter: **#CALIMEROProject**; **#LCA**; **#LCC**; **#SLCA**; **#biobased**; **#sustainability**; **#bioeconomy**. All members can use them when writing tweets and retweeting.

5.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most popular networking online site. It is used for **connecting with people that work in similar or related fields, as well as sharing knowledge**. CTA is responsible of the management of this channel, but any partner can be included as administrator of the page in order to upload information. Partners are free to ask for this access to CTA.

LinkedIn should be updated regularly, with **at least 1 post every month**. Posts that include multimedia elements are highly recommended. The language will be clear but technical or scientific terms can be used if necessary. This network can help the project reach a lot of interesting stakeholders from the different professional areas and to generate engagement and a good visibility for **CALIMERO**.

5.2.3 YouTube

This social media channel is **the most visited video network**, with millions of visitors. We are considering to open this network and upload project videos as well as videos of project members talking about their organization and work. As the topics addressed in the project can be hard to understand for the general public, **we can ease this task through easy and short project videos**.

This network will be updated regularly, or whenever the consortium members deliver content to CTA. All members can send videos or information to CTA. The content will be uploaded in English, but some content may be displayed in the other languages of the project members.

5.3 **Communication materials**

CTA is in charge of developing communication materials to promote the **CALIMERO** project. Partners must inform with enough time in advance if they need some of these materials for events participation or other requirements.

A press release has been produced for CALIMERO and has been sent to several interested parties to network with throughout the project. It was uploaded to the website, where it can be downloaded, and translated into other languages and is available in English, Spanish, German and Italian.

The **project brochure** is being designed and it will be printed and taken to any event or activity involving the project for its promotion and visibility. **Posters, factsheets, videos and other communication materials will be developed during the project**.

5.4 **Communication campaigns**

In some moments of the project, it is important to communicate **CALIMERO** findings, evolution or milestones with a special emphasis. **That is when communication campaigns are necessary to spread the message further**. These campaigns may include:

- Press releases.
- Publications in online and printed media.
- Special social media campaigns.
- Promotion of events and workshops.

These campaigns will be carried out in specific moments of the project and **will require specific tools and strategies to succeed** and reach as many people as possible or achieve specific campaign goals.

5.5 **Reporting events**

Partners of the consortium will **attend to relevant events, conferences and workshops**. They should be actively involved in seeking opportunities **to present and showcase the project in their own countries and at a**

European level.

The participation in events must be **previously communicated to CTA** (to make visible activities through communication channels), and after the event, every partner must report about the activity: **sum-up, number of attendees, pictures, publications, presentations, press clipping**, etc.

If results are going to be shared in an event, partners need to inform or **ask permission from the Exploitation Board to do so before the event**.

5.6 Support from the European Commission

The support to the **CALIMERO** project by the European Union must be recognised in all the dissemination and communication tools and materials. Any communication and dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

a) display the EU flag and the text Funded by the European Union. You can download them [here](#).

b) include the following text: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

6 EVALUATION PROCESS: KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

CTA coordinates the Communication and Dissemination Plan of **CALIMERO** and its activities **with the involvement of all the members of the consortium**. Each partner will make use of its communication tools and channels, networks and collaboration to reach the stakeholders of the project and build the **CALIMERO** community.

CTA compiles all the information about the events attended, upcoming events, other networking and collaborative activities, as well as the impacts on media. These are the minimum KPI for the project:

Table 4. Key performance indicators for CALIMERO

Activity	Indicators	Target	Schedule/Frequency
Website	# of Visits # of visitors	5.500 2000	M48
Social media	# of Followers	Twitter 200 LinkedIn 300 YouTube 150	M1-M48
Newsletter	# of Newsletters	3	One per year
Press releases	# of Press releases	3	Yearly
Videos	# of Visualisations	200 per video	M1-M48
Brochure	# of Brochure receivers	Handed 1.000 Downloaded 300	M9- First version M24- Project progress
Scientific publications	# of publications	8	M48
Workshops	# of Workshops organised # of workshops attended	5 5	M48
Conferences	# of presentations	9	Until M48

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Activity	Indicators	Target	Schedule/Frequency
	# attended	<u>6</u>	
Training for early-career researchers	# of Trainings	<u>2</u>	M48
Other Events	# of Events attended	<u>6</u>	M48
	# of Events organised	<u>2</u>	
Clustering activities	# of actions attended	<u>4</u>	M48
Meetings with sustainability/LCA/ bioeconomy associations or platforms	# of Meeting attended	<u>5</u>	M48

6.1 Foreseen activities in 2023

For the year 2023, **several communication and dissemination have been foreseen** for the visibility of the project. They are detailed in this chart:

Table 5: Foreseen activities in 2023

Type of activity	Estimated
Press release	<u>1</u>
Newsletter	<u>1</u>
Scientific publications	<u>1</u>
Communication materials	<u>2</u>
Social media	<u>+50</u> Twitter <u>+50</u> LinkedIn
Website	<u>+1000</u> visits
Post and news	<u>12</u>
Conference participation	<u>3</u>
Joint activities with other projects	<u>3</u>
Workshop	<u>1</u>

7 DISSEMINATION: OPEN ACCESS

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable. 'Scientific' refers to all academic disciplines. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can mean:

- Peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals).
- Research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

7.1 Peer-reviewed scientific research articles

Open access to scientific publications means free online access for any user. Although there are no legally binding definitions of 'access' or 'open access' in this context, authoritative definitions of open access appear in key political declarations including:

- the 2002 [Budapest Declaration](#)
- the 2003 [Berlin Declaration](#)

Under these definitions, 'access' includes not only basic elements - the right to read, download and print – but also **the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine**.

The 2 main routes to open access are:

- **Self-archiving / 'green' open access** – the author, or a representative, archives (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication. Some publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed.
- **Open access publishing / 'gold' open access** - an article is immediately published in open access mode. In this model, the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers. The most common business model is based on one-off payments by authors. These costs, often referred to as Article Processing Charges (APCs) are usually borne by the researcher's university or research institute or the agency funding the research. In other cases, the costs of open access publishing are covered by subsidies or other funding models.

In the context of research funding, **open access requirements do not imply an obligation to publish results**. The decision to publish is entirely up to the grant beneficiaries. **Open access becomes an issue *only if* publication is chosen as a means of dissemination**.

Moreover, open access does not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially, e.g. through patenting. The decision on whether to publish through open access must come after the more general decision on whether to publish directly or to first seek protection.

7.2 Open access to research data

Open access to **research data** refers to the right to access and reuse digital research data under the terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement.

Research data refers to **information**, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation.

In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. **The focus is on research data that is available in digital form**.

Users can normally access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate openly accessible research data free of charge.

7.3 Mandate on open access to publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

To meet this requirement, beneficiaries must, at the very least, **ensure that any scientific peer-reviewed publications can be read online, downloaded and printed**. Since any further rights - such as the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine - make publications more useful, beneficiaries should make every effort to provide as many of these options as possible.

Peer-reviewed publications are **those assessed by other scholars**. Peer review is typically, though not exclusively, organised by the journal or publisher to which an article or manuscript is submitted. However, new approaches are expected to become more prevalent in years to come. The dominant type of scientific publication is the journal article. Grant beneficiaries are also strongly encouraged to provide open access to other types of scientific publications including:

- monographs
- books

- conference proceedings
- grey literature (informally published written material not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g., reports)

The open-access mandate comprises 2 steps:

1. depositing publications in repositories
2. providing open access to them.